

Mixing and indirect CP violation in two-body charm decays at LHCb

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Abstract

The copious number of D^0 decays collected by the LHCb experiment during 2011–2016 allows the test of the violation of the CP symmetry in the decay of charm quarks with unprecedented precision, approaching for the first time the expectations of the Standard Model. We present the latest measurements of LHCb of mixing and indirect CP violation in the decay of D^0 mesons into two charged hadrons. All the results for A_Γ , mixing and CP violation with $D^0 \rightarrow K^\pm \pi^\mp$ decays and y_{CP} are the most precise to date and are still limited by the statistical uncertainty. No evidence of CP violation has been found yet.

1 Introduction

Whereas the violation of the charge-parity symmetry (CPV) in down-type quarks has been known for many years, CPV in the decay of up-type quarks has not been observed yet. The $D^0-\bar{D}^0$ is the only system of oscillating neutral mesons which contains up-type quarks. The Standard Model (SM) predicts for it CPV at a level below 10^{-3} [1, 2], but CPV might be enhanced by new particles beyond the SM which leave unaffected its magnitude for down-type quarks [1, 3–6].

The LHCb detector [7, 8] has collected the largest sample of decays of D^0 mesons into charged hadrons available to date, thanks to the large production cross-section of $c\bar{c}$ pairs at the LHC [9, 10]. We review the most recent measurements of mixing and indirect CPV in the decay of D^0 mesons into two charged hadrons performed by LHCb, which have a precision comparable to the SM expectations for CPV . The measurements were performed with the data of Run 1 (2011–2012, 1 fb^{-1} of integrated luminosity of pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 7\text{ TeV}$ and 2 fb^{-1} at $\sqrt{s} = 8\text{ TeV}$) and of the first two years of Run 2 (2015–2016, 2 fb^{-1} at $\sqrt{s} = 13\text{ TeV}$).

2 Measurement of A_Γ with Run 1 data

An asymmetry between the time-dependent decay rates of D^0 and \bar{D}^0 mesons into the same CP eigenstate $f = K^+K^-$ or $f = \pi^+\pi^-$ would be a clear indication of CPV . Since

the mixing parameters $x \equiv (m_2 - m_1)/\Gamma$ and $y \equiv (\Gamma_2 - \Gamma_1)/2\Gamma$ are $< 10^{-2}$ [11]¹ and the direct CP asymmetry is below 10^{-3} [12, 13], it can be written as

$$A_{CP}(t) = \frac{\Gamma(D^0 \rightarrow f, t) - \Gamma(\bar{D}^0 \rightarrow f, t)}{\Gamma(D^0 \rightarrow f, t) + \Gamma(\bar{D}^0 \rightarrow f, t)} \approx a_{CP}^{\text{dir},f} - A_\Gamma \left(\frac{t}{\tau} \right),$$

where $a_{CP}^{\text{dir},f}$ is the direct CP asymmetry into final state f , τ is the lifetime of the D^0 meson and

$$A_\Gamma \approx \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\left| \frac{q}{p} \right| - \left| \frac{p}{q} \right| \right) y \cos \phi_f - \left(\left| \frac{q}{p} \right| + \left| \frac{p}{q} \right| \right) x \sin \phi_f \right], \quad (1)$$

where p, q are the complex coefficients of the decomposition of the mass eigenstates $|D_{1,2}\rangle \equiv p|D^0\rangle \pm q|\bar{D}^0\rangle$ and $\phi_f \equiv \arg[(-q\mathcal{A}(\bar{D}^0 \rightarrow f))/(p\mathcal{A}(D^0 \rightarrow f))]$. A non-zero value of A_Γ would signal indirect CPV in the mixing ($|q/p| \neq 1$) or in the interference between the mixing and the decay ($\phi_f \neq 0$).² Since indirect CPV is measured to be small [11], A_Γ is approximately equal to $A_\Gamma \approx y(|q/p| - 1) - x\phi_f$.

The LHCb collaboration has measured A_Γ with Run 1 data, using the sign of the soft pion in the $D^{*+} \rightarrow D^0\pi_s^+$ strong decay,³ where the D^{*+} is produced in the pp collisions, to determine the flavour at production of the D^0 meson [14]. The signal yields, corresponding to 9.6 (3.0) million $D^0 \rightarrow K^+K^-$ ($D^0 \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$) decays, are measured in bins of decay time and their asymmetry is fitted with a linear function, extracting A_Γ as the opposite of the slope.

Even if the D^0 final state is charge-symmetric and is not affected by detection asymmetries, the momentum-dependent charge asymmetries in the detection of the π_s^+ used to infer the flavour of the D^0 , shown in Fig. 1, can bias the measurement of A_Γ by a quantity much larger than its statistical uncertainty. In fact, owing to time-momentum correlations induced by the trigger requirements on flight distance-related quantities, these momentum-dependent asymmetries translate into time-dependent charge asymmetries that can mimic a fake value of A_Γ . These asymmetries are removed by equalising the 3D momentum distributions of π_s^+ and π_s^- mesons. The effectiveness of the method is checked on the $D^0 \rightarrow K^-\pi^+$ control sample (87.5 million candidates), where the slope of the time-dependent asymmetry is known to be zero within the experimental uncertainty, and the weighing is verified not to bias significantly the measurement of A_Γ .

The final results of the fits to the time-dependent asymmetry (Fig. 2) are

$$\begin{aligned} A_\Gamma^{KK} &= (-3.0 \pm 3.2 \pm 1.0) \cdot 10^{-4}, \\ A_\Gamma^{\pi\pi} &= (4.6 \pm 5.8 \pm 1.2) \cdot 10^{-4}, \end{aligned}$$

where the first uncertainties are statistical and the second ones systematic. If universality of ϕ between K^+K^- and $\pi^+\pi^-$ final states is assumed, as expected in the SM [1, 15], the two values can be averaged to yield $A_\Gamma = (-1.3 \pm 2.8 \pm 1.0) \cdot 10^{-4}$.

The systematic uncertainty is dominated by the contamination of the data sample from secondary decays in which the D^{*+} is not produced in the pp collision but in the decay of a b -hadron. Since the average lifetime of b -hadrons is higher than that of the

¹We define $m_{1,2}$ and $\Gamma_{1,2}$ to be the masses and the decay widths of the mass eigenstates $|D_{1,2}\rangle$, with the convention that $|D_1\rangle$ is the CP -odd state in the limit of CP conservation.

²We use the convention that $\phi_f = 0$ in the limit of no CPV .

³Charge-conjugate processes are implied throughout.

Figure 1: (Left) distribution and (right) asymmetry of the π_s^+ used to infer the flavour of the D^0 as a function of $\theta_x = \arctan(p_x/p_z)$ and $k = 1/\sqrt{p_x^2 + p_z^2}$. The angle θ_x is multiplied by the charge q_s of the π_s to remove large acceptance asymmetries due to the dipole magnet of LHCb which bends particles of opposite charge in opposite directions along x .

Figure 2: Asymmetry between the number D^0 and \bar{D}^0 decays as a function of decay time in units of D^0 lifetime for (left) $D^0 \rightarrow K^+K^-$ and (right) $D^0 \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ decays. The slope of the linear fit overlaid is equal to $-A_\Gamma$.

D^0 and the flight distance of the D^0 is calculated from the pp vertex to improve the resolution on the decay time, the measured decay time of secondary decays is biased towards higher times and the measured fraction of secondary decays increases with time. As the production asymmetry of the D^{*+} mesons is different from that of b -hadrons, this translates in a time-dependent asymmetry which can bias the measurement of A_Γ . The contribution to the asymmetry from secondary decays is not subtracted and accounts for the full size of the systematic uncertainty, $1.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$.

A statistically independent measurement of A_Γ at LHCb also uses Run 1 data, but identifies the flavour of the D^0 at production from the sign of the muon in the decay $\bar{B} \rightarrow D^0 \mu^- X$, where \bar{B} is a b -hadron and X stands for arbitrary unreconstructed particles [16]. The statistical uncertainty of this measurement is a factor 2.4 larger than the one of the analysis presented above, owing to the lower production cross-section for $b\bar{b}$ pairs with respect to that of $c\bar{c}$ pairs in the pp collisions at the LHC. When it is combined with the previous measurement, one obtains $A_\Gamma = (-2.9 \pm 2.8) \cdot 10^{-4}$, which dominates the world average of A_Γ .

Figure 3: Representation of the two main amplitudes of (left) RS and (right) WS decays. Dashed lines represent suppressed mixing and doubly Cabibbo-suppressed (DCS) processes.

3 Mixing and indirect CPV in $D^0 \rightarrow K^\pm \pi^\mp$ decays with 2011–2016 data

The right-sign (RS) decay $D^{*+} \rightarrow D^0(\rightarrow K^- \pi^+) \pi^+$ and the much rarer wrong-sign (WS) decay $D^{*+} \rightarrow D^0(\rightarrow K^+ \pi^-) \pi^+$ can take place with or without mixing (Fig. 3). However, since the ratio of the branching fraction of the doubly Cabibbo-suppressed (DCS) $D^0 \rightarrow K^+ \pi^-$ decay to that of the Cabibbo-favoured (CF) $D^0 \rightarrow K^- \pi^+$ decay is $\approx 3.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and the mixing parameters are small [11], mixing is negligible for RS decays, whereas it becomes more and more important for WS decays as time passes. Therefore, the ratio of the number of WS to that of RS decays increases with time as

$$R^\pm(t) = \frac{\Gamma_{\text{WS}}^\pm(t)}{\Gamma_{\text{RS}}^\pm(t)} = R_D^\pm + \sqrt{R_D^\pm} y'^\pm \left(\frac{t}{\tau}\right) + \frac{(x'^\pm)^2 + (y'^\pm)^2}{4} \left(\frac{t}{\tau}\right)^2, \quad (2)$$

where positive and negative signs denote initial D^0 and \bar{D}^0 flavours, $R_D^+ \equiv |\mathcal{A}(D^0 \rightarrow K^+ \pi^-)/\mathcal{A}(D^0 \rightarrow K^- \pi^+)|^2$, $R_D^- \equiv |\mathcal{A}(\bar{D}^0 \rightarrow K^- \pi^+)/\mathcal{A}(\bar{D}^0 \rightarrow K^+ \pi^-)|^2$, $x'^\pm \equiv |q/p|^{\pm 1} [x \cos(\delta \pm \phi) + y \sin(\delta \pm \phi)]$ and $y'^\pm \equiv |q/p|^{\pm 1} [y \cos(\delta \pm \phi) - x \sin(\delta \pm \phi)]$. The constant term in Eq. (2) corresponds to the DCS amplitude of the WS decay, the term quadratic in time to the CF decay after mixing and the linear term to the interference between the two amplitudes. In the limit of no CPV , x' and y' are the rotation of x and y with the strong phase between suppressed and favoured amplitudes, $\mathcal{A}(D^0 \rightarrow K^+ \pi^-)/\mathcal{A}(\bar{D}^0 \rightarrow K^+ \pi^-) = -\sqrt{R_D^-} e^{-i\delta}$, which was measured at CLEO and BESIII experiments [17, 18]. Having $R_D^+ \neq R_D^-$ would be a sign of direct CPV , while $x'^+ \neq x'^-$ or $y'^+ \neq y'^-$ would be an indication of indirect CPV .

The LHCb collaboration has performed a measurement of $R^\pm(t)$ with the data collected in 2011–2016 [19]. The flavour at production of the D^0 meson is identified with the $D^{*+} \rightarrow D^0 \pi_s^+$ strong decay, and the yields are measured in bins of decay time from fits to the D^{*+} mass (Fig. 4). The detection efficiency of the π_s^+ and the production cross-section of the D^{*+} cancel in the ratio of WS to RS yield, and only the detection asymmetry of the final states $K^- \pi^+$ has to be corrected for. This is measured from data as $A_{\text{det}}(K^- \pi^+) = A_{\text{meas}}(D^+ \rightarrow K^- \pi^+ \pi^+) - A_{\text{meas}}(D^+ \rightarrow \bar{K}^0 \pi^+) + A(\bar{K}^0)$, where the kinematics of the various decays are reweighed to match that of the measured $D^0 \rightarrow K^\pm \pi^\mp$ decays. The production asymmetry of the D^+ cancel in the difference and CPV asymmetries in its decay can be neglected, whereas the value of $A(\bar{K}^0)$ at LHCb is calculated following Ref. [13].

The time-dependent ratios $R^\pm(t)$ are fitted under three assumptions, namely of no CPV ($R^+(t) = R^-(t)$), no direct CPV ($R_D^+ = R_D^-$) and allowing for both direct and indirect CPV . The results are displayed in Fig. 5 and in Table 1. No evidence of CPV is found. This measurement dominates the world average of the parameter y , but does not allow to establish whether x is non-zero owing to the smallness and the uncertainty on δ

Figure 4: Time-integrated yields for the (a) $D^0 \rightarrow K^- \pi^+$ and (b) $D^0 \rightarrow K^+ \pi^-$ sample, corresponding to 177 and 0.72 million candidates.

Figure 5: Efficiency-corrected ratios of WS to RS yields for (a) D^{*+} decays, (b) D^{*-} and (c) their differences as a function of decay time in units of D^0 lifetime. Projections of fits allowing for (dashed line) no CP violation, (dotted line) no direct CP violation and (solid line) direct and indirect CP violation are overlaid. The last two curves overlap.

and to the fact that x' enters in Eq. (2) only as a square and in the term quadratic in time.

The dominant systematic uncertainties are due to secondary decays, like for the measurement of A_Γ , and to wrong measurements of the charge of the π_s . This happens in events in which the cluster of the track of the π_s in the tracking stations upstream the magnet is wrongly matched to the cluster of an independent track in the tracking stations downstream it. Since the determination of the mass of the D^{*+} is dominated by the measurement of the angle between the π_s and the D^0 , it is measured correctly, even if with a lower resolution due to the wrong measurement of the π_s momentum. However, the π_s is assigned the wrong charge about half of times and the D meson is consequently assigned the wrong flavour, interchanging WS with RS decays. The probability of this misassignment has to be kept much smaller than the ratio between the branching fractions

Table 1: Results of fits for different CP -violation hypotheses. The first contribution to the uncertainties is statistical and the second systematic. Correlations include both statistical and systematic contributions.

Results [10^{-3}]		Correlations					
Direct and indirect CP violation							
Parameter	Value	R_D^+	y'^+	$(x'^+)^2$	R_D^-	y'^-	$(x'^-)^2$
R_D^+	$3.454 \pm 0.040 \pm 0.020$	1.000	-0.935	0.843	-0.012	-0.003	0.002
y'^+	$5.01 \pm 0.64 \pm 0.38$		1.000	-0.963	-0.003	0.004	-0.003
$(x'^+)^2$	$0.061 \pm 0.032 \pm 0.019$			1.000	0.002	-0.003	0.003
R_D^-	$3.454 \pm 0.040 \pm 0.020$				1.000	-0.935	0.846
y'^-	$5.54 \pm 0.64 \pm 0.38$					1.000	-0.964
$(x'^-)^2$	$0.016 \pm 0.033 \pm 0.020$						1.000
No direct CP violation							
Parameter	Value	R_D	y'^+	$(x'^+)^2$	y'^-	$(x'^-)^2$	
R_D	$3.454 \pm 0.028 \pm 0.014$	1.000	-0.883	0.745	-0.883	0.749	
y'^+	$5.01 \pm 0.48 \pm 0.29$		1.000	-0.944	0.758	-0.644	
$(x'^+)^2$	$0.061 \pm 0.026 \pm 0.016$			1.000	-0.642	0.545	
y'^-	$5.54 \pm 0.48 \pm 0.29$				1.000	-0.946	
$(x'^-)^2$	$0.016 \pm 0.026 \pm 0.016$					1.000	
No CP violation							
Parameter	Value	R_D	y'	x'^2			
R_D	$3.454 \pm 0.028 \pm 0.014$	1.000	-0.942	0.850			
y'	$5.28 \pm 0.45 \pm 0.27$		1.000	-0.963			
x'^2	$0.039 \pm 0.023 \pm 0.014$			1.000			

of WS to RS decays, $\approx 3.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$. The uncertainty on the size of the residual background which is not rejected by the neural network designed to do this [20] accounts for the second largest systematic uncertainty of the measurement.

4 Measurement of y_{CP} with Run 1 data

The y_{CP} parameter is defined as

$$y_{CP} \equiv \frac{\hat{\Gamma}(D^0 \rightarrow f) + \hat{\Gamma}(\bar{D}^0 \rightarrow f)}{2\Gamma} - 1,$$

where $f = K^+K^-$ or $f = \pi^+\pi^-$, $\hat{\Gamma}$ is the effective decay width that is measured when modelling the distribution of the decays with an exponential function $e^{-\hat{\Gamma}t}$ and Γ is the decay width of the D^0 meson that can be measured in the decays into the non CP -symmetric final state $D^0 \rightarrow K^-\pi^+$. Using the same parameters of Eq. (1), it can be expressed as

$$y_{CP} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\left| \frac{q}{p} \right| + \left| \frac{p}{q} \right| \right) y \cos \phi_f - \left(\left| \frac{q}{p} \right| - \left| \frac{p}{q} \right| \right) x \sin \phi_f \right]$$

Figure 6: Distribution of the D^0 mass with fit overlaid for (top) $D^0 \rightarrow K^+K^-$, (centre) $D^0 \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ and (bottom) $D^0 \rightarrow K^-\pi^+$ candidates. The total yields correspond to 0.88, 0.31 and 4.6 million events for the K^+K^- , $\pi^+\pi^-$ and $K^-\pi^+$ final states.

which, in the limit of small CPV , becomes $y_{CP} \approx y + y [(|q/p| - 1)^2 - \phi_f^2/2] / 2 - x\phi_f (|q/p| - 1)$. Therefore, $y_{CP} = y$ in the limit of no CPV , with CP -violating corrections that are quadratic in $(|q/p| - 1)$ and ϕ_f , whereas for A_Γ the corrections to zero were linear in the same CP -violating quantities. This means that, at the current level of precision, A_Γ is more sensitive to CPV , whereas y_{CP} is mostly a measurement of y .

The LHCb collaboration has measured y_{CP} with Run 1 data, determining the flavour at production of the D^0 from the sign of the muon in $\bar{B} \rightarrow D^0 \mu^- X$ decays [21]. The yields are measured in bins of decay time through a fit to the mass distribution of the D^0 (Fig. 6). Then, y_{CP} is measured through a χ^2 fit to the yield ratio of K^+K^- ($\pi^+\pi^-$) to $K^-\pi^+$ decays with the following function,

$$R_i = N \cdot A_i \cdot \frac{\int_{t_i}^{t_{i+1}} e^{-(\Gamma + \Delta_\Gamma)t} dt}{\int_{t_i}^{t_{i+1}} e^{-\Gamma t} dt},$$

where the subscript i denotes the time bin, N is a time-independent normalisation constant, A_i is the ratio of the acceptances for the two final states in the time bin i as measured with simulated events (Fig. 7 left) and the last term is the ratio of the probability density functions of K^+K^- ($\pi^+\pi^-$) to $K^-\pi^+$ decays integrated over the time bin i , with $y_{CP} = \Delta_\Gamma/\Gamma = (\hat{\Gamma}_f - \Gamma)/\Gamma$. This method, which was inspired by previous measurements of the lifetime of the D_s^+ and B_s^0 mesons at LHCb [22], allows to cancel the main acceptance and efficiency effects in the ratio, reducing the impact of possible disagreements between simulation and data on the final measurement.

The method is validated through several null tests to prove that the corrections from the simulated events are reliable. The most sensitive one considers the time-dependent yield ratio between two non-overlapping samples of $D^0 \rightarrow K^-\pi^+$ decays, divided according

Figure 7: (Left) ratio of the acceptances as measured in simulated events and (right) acceptance-corrected signal-yield ratio of (top) $D^0 \rightarrow K^+K^-$ and (bottom) $D^0 \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ to $D^0 \rightarrow K^-\pi^+$ decays as a function of D^0 decay time. The fit projection is overlaid on the right plots. The variations of the ratio of the acceptances over time, $\mathcal{O}(6\%)$, are mainly due to the different impact of the trigger requirements on the χ_{IP}^2 of the daughters of the D^0 on different decay channels.

to the value of the χ_{IP}^2 of the decay products of the D^0 .⁴ For these samples, Δ_Γ is expected to be zero within the experimental uncertainty. The trigger requirement on the χ_{IP}^2 is the main cause of different time-dependent acceptances for the $D^0 \rightarrow K^+K^-$ ($D^0 \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$) and $D^0 \rightarrow K^-\pi^+$ decay channels, causing the ratio of their acceptances to vary by $\approx 6\%$ over time (Fig. 7 left). For the two $D^0 \rightarrow K^-\pi^+$ subsamples, the variation of the ratio increases to $\approx 30\%$, so that the impact of possible mismodellings of the acceptances in the simulated events is expected to be larger, too. In a complementary test, the difference between the decay widths of the D^+ and D^0 mesons is measured from the yield ratio of $D^+ \rightarrow K^-\pi^+\pi^+$ to $D^0 \rightarrow K^-\pi^+$ decays. Since the number of particles and the topology of the two final states are different, also in this case possible mismodellings in the simulated events are expected to cancel in the ratio with lower precision than for the $D^0 \rightarrow K^+K^-$ ($D^0 \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$) to $D^0 \rightarrow K^-\pi^+$ ratio. In addition, the ratio between the two lifetimes is ≈ 2.5 , thus the test is also sensitive to possible biases on the measurement that are linear in Δ_Γ . Both cross-checks agree with the expectations with an uncertainty smaller than that of the measurement of y_{CP} .

The results of the fit to the time-dependent ratio of the yields (Fig. 7 right) are

$$y_{CP}^{KK} = (0.63 \pm 0.15 \pm 0.11)\%,$$

$$y_{CP}^{\pi\pi} = (0.38 \pm 0.28 \pm 0.15)\%,$$

where the first uncertainties are statistical and the second ones, which are dominated by the statistical uncertainty on the ratio of the acceptances due to the limited size of the sample of simulated events, systematic. If universality is assumed [1, 15], the averaged result is $y_{CP} = (0.57 \pm 0.13 \pm 0.09)\%$, in agreement and as precise as the previous world average $y_{CP} = (0.835 \pm 0.155)\%$. The measured value of y_{CP} agrees with the world average of $y = (0.67^{+0.06}_{-0.13})\%$, as well: as expected, no evidence of CPV is detectable for y_{CP} with the current experimental precision.

⁴The χ_{IP}^2 is defined as the difference in the vertex-fit χ^2 of the pp vertex with and without the track under consideration.

5 Conclusions

The world most precise measurements of mixing and indirect CPV in the two-body decays of D^0 mesons have been presented. No evidence of CPV in the decay of charm quarks has been observed yet. The 4 fb^{-1} of pp collision data collected in 2017–2018 at $\sqrt{s} = 13\text{ TeV}$ will allow in the next few years a further increase of the precision of all measurements, which are not limited by the systematic uncertainty,⁵ allowing starting to test the expectations of the SM for CPV .

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⁵The systematic uncertainty on y_{CP} can be reduced increasing the size of the sample of simulated events used to calculate the time-dependent acceptances of $D^0 \rightarrow f$ decays.

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